

Phylogeny, lipid composition, pigment signature, and growth of the fish-killer *Heterosigma akashiwo* from Chilean Patagonia

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Abstract

The raphidophyte *Heterosigma akashiwo* is widely distributed in coastal ecosystems where it has caused massive events of fish mortality and shellfish damage. In April 2021, high cell abundances of *H. akashiwo* ($> 70,000$ cells mL⁻¹) killed $> 6,000$ tons of salmon in the Chilean fjords. This study investigated the molecular phylogeny, pigment composition, fatty acid profile, and cell growth of the *H. akashiwo* (strain CREAN_HA03) from Chilean waters. A phylogenetic reconstruction based on the large sub-unit ribosomal nucleotide showed that the Chilean strain belongs to the *H. akashiwo* clade. The genetic distance was 0.00 relative to strains from Japan, Australia, U.S.A., China, and New Zealand. The pigment signature showed that the CREAN_HA03 strain is mainly dominated by fucoxanthin (48.4%), chlorophyll c2 (18.3%), chlorophyll *a* (14.7%), and violaxanthin (9.8%). A factorial T-S growth experiment showed a μ_{\max} of 0.48 d⁻¹ at 17 °C and salinity of 35. The maximum cell abundance of $\sim 50,000$ cells mL⁻¹ was reached at 12°C and a salinity of 25. The fatty acid profile exhibited a high abundance of polyunsaturated fatty acids: 20.94% palmitic acid (16:0), 13.04% EPA (20:5 ω 3), and 10.44% stearidonic acid (18:4 ω 3), which have all been described as highly cytotoxic against fish gill tissue. Further characterization of more Chilean *H. akashiwo* isolates is needed to understand the precise ichthyotoxic mechanisms and environmental drivers that trigger massive bloom events in Chilean Patagonia.

Keywords: Raphidophytes, ichthyotoxins, Chilean fjords, Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs)

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Introduction

Heterosigma akashiwo is a small raphidophyte widely distributed in coastal ecosystems. This species produces ichthyotoxic blooms in different parts of the world, responsible for economically devastating fish kill events. This species is a marine phytoflagellate, however, it can be found in estuaries, indicating its ability to tolerate a large range of salinities (Martinez *et al.*, 2010). *Heterosigma akashiwo* has also been previously described its ability to grow at a broad range of temperatures (eurythermal species).

In Chilean waters, the first *H. akashiwo* salmon-killing event was reported in September of 1988, which ignited the phytoplankton monitoring program in Chile (Mardones *et al.*, 2012). After this event, the raphidophyte did not bloom again in high cell densities until April of 2021 in the Comau fjord, Northern Patagonia (42°22.166' S, 72°27.30' W), causing a massive mortality of salmon (> 6,000 tons) (SERNAPESCA, 2021; www.sernapesca.cl).

It has been demonstrated that *H. akashiwo* produces molecules that have a similar toxic effect to brevetoxins, however this molecule is not structurally related to the brevetoxin group. Some authors have proposed that the toxicity is due to high concentrations of lipids like PUFAs (Dorantes-Aranda *et al.*, 2015). However, the cytotoxic compounds produced by *H. akashiwo* are still unknown.

The main objective of this study was to define the phylogenetic position, pigment signature and fatty acid profile of a Chilean *H. akashiwo* strain, as well as the environmental conditions that might promote its growth in southern Chilean waters.

Material and Methods

Microalgae culture conditions

One monoclonal culture of *H. akashiwo* (CREAN_HA03 strain) was isolated from the Comau fjord in 2019 (42° 22.166' S, 72° 27.30' W; Los Lagos Region). The CREAN_HA03 strain was maintained in culture at the CREAN-IFOP algae collection in Puerto Montt, Chile. Non-axenic cultures were grown in L1 medium (Guillard and Ryther, 1962) at 15°C in sterile filtered (0.22 µm), in seawater at a salinity of 33 at 100 µmol photon m⁻² s⁻¹ (cool white fluorescence lamps) under a 18:6 h light:dark cycle.

DNA extraction, amplification, sequencing and phylogeny

A detailed protocol for genetic analyses performed at the CREAN laboratory is described in Mardones *et al.* (2020). Briefly, a culture of *H. akashiwo* was harvested and concentrated to amplify the D1/D2 region of the 28S ribosomal gene using the D1/D2 primers. The PCR products were visualized and then purified using the Illustra GFX PCR DNA and gel band purification kit (GE Healthcare), and sent to MacroGen Sequencing Facility (MacroGen®, South Korea) for ribosomal regions sequencing in both directions. Phylogenetic reconstruction was performed using the sequences published in GenBank using an alignment of 920 bp. For genetic outputs, a maximum likelihood analysis (ML), Likelihood Ratio Test (aLRT), bootstrap analysis (1,000 replicates), and Bayesian analyses were used.

HPLC pigment analysis

For pigment analysis, a detailed protocol is described in Mardones *et al.* (2020). Briefly, 50 mL of the CREAN_HA03 strain

in exponential growth phase were filtered (0.45 μm) and collected cells were extracted in 1 mL acetone after probe sonication (60s) and kept for 24 h at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Pigments were quantified using a Shimadzu high-resolution liquid chromatograph (HPLC), and SPD-M20A diode array detector (DAD). Chromatographic separation was carried out by using an ACE C18 PFP column at $40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Mobil phase A was prepared with methanol: 225 mM ammonium acetate (82:12 v:v) and mobile phase B with ethanol. The gradient program was set at a flow rate of 1.0 mL min^{-1} . Seven certified reference standards (DHI Laboratory Products, Hoersholm, Denmark) were used for the correct identification of these pigments.

Lipid extraction and analysis

For lipid analysis, a detailed protocol is described in Mardones *et al.* (2020). Briefly, filters containing the CREAN_HA03 strain were extracted using dichloromethane / methanol/ water (1:2:0.8, v/v/v). After phase separation, the extracted lipids were transmethylated for two h at $85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. After the addition of water, the mixture was extracted three times to obtain fatty acid methyl esters (FAME). Samples were prepared to a known volume with the internal injection standard solution (19:0 FAME) and analysed by gas chromatography. Samples were injected by a split/splitless injector and an Agilent Technologies 7683B Series autosampler in splitless mode at an oven temperature of $120\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. After one min, the oven temperature was increased to $270\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$, then to $310\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$. FAME were identified by assessment against retention times of laboratory standards. Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) analyses

were performed for selected samples for confirmation of FAME identification.

Growth of H. akashiwo under different temperatures and salinities

The experiments with *H. akashiwo* (CREAN_HA03 strain) were carried out in triplicate using sterile flasks, each containing 45 mL of L1 culture medium inoculated with 300 cells mL^{-1} . The growth rate and culture yield were studied using a crossed factorial design under six conditions, obtained from combining three salinities (25, 30 and 35) and two temperatures (12 and $17\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). These different salinities and temperature ranges tested are commonly found within the inner Patagonian fjords.

To prevent modifications in the physiological response of *H. akashiwo* due to changes in temperature and salinity, cultures were pre-acclimated to the desired experimental conditions via stepwise transfer over a defined period (> 20 days). The experiment was carried out for 19 days, with samples taken every 2 – 3 days. Cell density was determined immediately after sampling, based on buffered glutaraldehyde fixed cells quantified under an inverted light microscope using a Fuch-Rosenthal chamber. In every sampling date, the mean cell number obtained from the three replicates was used to calculate the growth rate μ (d^{-1}) according to (Guillard and Hargraves, 1993):

$$\mu = \frac{\ln(c_1/c_0)}{t_1 - t_0}$$

were c_0 and c_1 are the cell densities (cells mL^{-1}) at the beginning (t_0) and end (t_1) of the incubation period (days), respectively.

Results and Discussion

Bayesian phylogenetic and Maximum Likelihood analysis of the LSU D1-D2 region showed that the CREAM_HA03 sequence is in a monophyletic clade that comprises only *H. akashiwo* sequences, supported by one probability value (Fig. 1). The monophyletic clade showed that the Chilean sequence of *Heterosigma* has a genetic distance of 0.00 relative to the sequences reported from Japan, Australian, U.S.A., Denmark, China and New Zealand. The genetic distance with other strains from Brazil, Canada, Korea, and New Zealand was 0.001. The distances with *H. minor* were estimated in 0.064. Previous reports have shown that this species has low genetic variability at the intraspecific level among strains of different parts of the world (Bowers *et al.*, 2006), which is in line with the results reported in this study.

The HPLC pigment analysis of the Chilean strain (CREAM_HA03) showed that the most abundant pigment is the carotenoid fucoxanthin, with 48% of the total pigments, followed by violoxanthin with 14% of the sample. Chlorophyll c2 was a significant pigment with 18% of the sample. The carotenoids fucoxanthin and violaxanthin are usually the most abundant secondary pigments among world-wide distributed *H. akashiwo* strains (Martínez *et al.*, 2010), as well as in Chilean strains (this study; Gómez *et al.*, 2021). This chemotaxonomic feature might help for future monitoring of this raphidophyte in Chilean waters using satellite ocean colour data.

The fatty acid profile of *H. akashiwo* strain was dominated by saturated fatty acid (SFA) followed by PUFA (Table 1). Around 20.94%

of the total fatty acid was palmitic acid (16:00, SFA), 13.04% EPA (20:5 ω 3, PUFA), and 10.44% stearidonic acid (18:4 ω 3, PUFA). These lipids have been described as cytotoxic against the RTgill-W1 rainbow trout gill cell line (Dorantes-Aranda *et al.*, 2015; Mardones *et al.*, 2015). This is the first study describing the lipid composition of a Chilean *H. akashiwo* strain. These results may assist in future studies pursuing the understanding of the ichthyotoxic mechanism in *H. akashiwo*, especially their link with the potential production of ROS by this raphidophyte.

Fig. 1. Phylogeny of the (A) large subunit (LSU rDNA) sequence of the Chilean *H. akashiwo* strain and related species. In bold is the Chilean CREAM sequence from this study.

The response of *H. akashiwo* strain CREAN_HA03 to changes in temperature and salinity was significantly different in terms of maximum cell biomass. The maximum cell abundance was $\sim 50,000$ cells mL^{-1} at 12°C and salinity of 25 (Fig. 2). However, the growth rate (μ) was not significantly different due to temperature and salinity changes. The highest μ_{max} (0.48 d^{-1}) was reached at salinity of 35 and at 17°C , meanwhile the lowest μ_{max} (0.38 d^{-1}) was reached at a salinity of 25 and at 17°C .

Table 1. Top three most abundant fatty acids quantified in the Patagonian *H. akashiwo* (strain CREAN_HA03) (as percentage of total fatty acids).

Fatty acids	Mean	SD
SFA		
16:00	20.94	0.14
PUFA		
18:4 ω 3	10.44	0.13
20:5 ω 3	13.04	0.15

Abbreviations: SFA, saturated fatty acids; PUFA, polyunsaturated fatty acids.

Fig. 2. *In vitro* growth of *H. akashiwo* at (A) 12°C and (B) 17°C , and at three different salinities.

These results point to the fact that that Chilean *H. akashiwo* can grow in different conditions of salinity and temperature, euryhaline and eurythermal characteristics that have been described for other world-wide distributed *H. akashiwo* strains (Martínez *et al.*, 2010). These characteristics provide a clear advantage over other microalgae species in highly variable estuarine ecosystems. A pending question is: “why did this species bloom after almost 20 years in the Chilean fjords if it presents such a high phenotypic plasticity?”. It is possible that the undergoing climate change scenario is triggering other important environmental factors such as enhanced water stratification and high-water retention rates that might be contributing to these unexpected HAB events.

This study is the first describing the genetic position and the lipid composition of a Chilean strain of the raphidophyte *H. akashiwo*. Future research should focus on the toxic mechanism of this specie, and how other factors (ie., nutrient concentrations) can affect its growth in a complex environment such as the Patagonian fjords.

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